

ENHANCING ESP COURSE DELIVERY THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD: A CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT APPROACH

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Annotasiya. Ushbu tezis maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tilini (ESP) o‘qitishda Kayzen usulini tatbiq etishni o‘rganadi va kursni o‘tkazish, talabalarning faolligini va ta’lim natijalarini yaxshilash uchun Kayzen tamoyillarini tatbiq etishni o‘rganadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Kayzen usuli, Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP), Kayzen tamoyillari

Аннотация: В этом тезисе исследуется применение метода Кайдзен при преподавании курсов английского языка для специальных целей (ESP), а также исследуются принципы Кайдзен для улучшения преподавания курса, вовлеченности студентов и результатов обучения.

Ключевые слова: Метод Кайдзен, курс английского языка для специальных целей (ESP), принципы Кайдзен

Abstract. This thesis explores implementing the Kaizen method in teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP) courses, and it examines the principles of Kaizen to enhance course delivery, student engagement, and learning outcomes.

Keywords: Kaizen method, ESP course, principles of Kaizen

Kaizen, a Japanese philosophy focused on continuous improvement, has been widely applied in various sectors, including manufacturing and business. First, it was introduced by Masaaki Imai's book 'Kaizen: The Key to Japan's Competitive Success' introduced the term KAIZEN, now recognized worldwide as a crucial pillar of long-term competitive strategy, resulting in superior results.

Since Kaizen focuses on making small, incremental changes that lead to significant improvements over time (a Japanese term meaning "change for better"), it

can be implemented as well in an ESP course by setting elements based on these principles. Implementing Kaizen in teaching an ESP course is about creating a dynamic learning environment where continuous improvement is part of the culture. It is a collaborative effort involving teachers, students, and the broader educational community, all working together to enhance the quality of education. Its core principles are continuous improvement, teamwork, quality circles, standardization, observation, and empowering people.

Scholars have recognized the potential of the Kaizen methodology, traditionally celebrated in manufacturing, for its application in the educational sector, including teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP) courses. The core principle of Kaizen in education is continuous improvement, focusing on small, incremental changes that lead to significant enhancements in teaching quality and student learning outcomes. German professor at the South Westphalia University of Applied Sciences Ingo Kregel in his research highlighted the application of Kaizen in university teaching through action research, combining the philosophy of continuous improvement with evaluations of student courses, in which Kaizen was found to successfully improve course quality, especially in the first two years of newly developed courses.

However, by integrating this new approach, challenges in ESP teaching such as the lack of student engagement, the static course content, and the need for more adaptable teaching methods should be taken into consideration. In this term, the core-based principles of Kaizen can be implemented by refining them in teaching ESP. To resolve the challenges, it is suggested to set clear objectives by identifying the specific needs of students. According to Harrison (1996), to accumulate some information that concerns the learning needs, to define the purpose of the targeted courses, and to determine the suitable content need analysis is immediately needed. So, based on the needs analysis teachers can set clear, specific, and achievable learning objectives for the course.

The next step to avoiding challenges can be engaging in continuous assessment by providing regular and constructive feedback to students on their performance. Evans

(2013) outlines models and theories of feedback that highlight the variety of approaches to feedback and its significant positive impact on student achievement and engagement. It is suggested that feedback must be clear, direct, and tailored to individual student needs to foster effective learning. Teachers should regularly evaluate the effectiveness of teaching methods and materials, seeking ways to improve them.

Indeed, to improve the ESP course teachers cannot do without motivating students which is the third step. To motivate students to participate actively in the learning process, teachers should encourage them to share their ideas on improving the course and their learning strategies. Moreover, teachers may force educators to collaborate with peers because peer observations can provide new perspectives and ideas for improvement.

The fourth step is embracing small changes. Implementing small changes to teaching practices or materials and observing their impact, reduces risk and makes it easier to adapt. The fifth step might be utilizing technology. Using technology can help to enhance learning and teaching processes. This could include language learning apps, online resources, or digital platforms for collaboration and feedback. Several scholars have extensively explored the use of technology in education, highlighting its potential to transform learning and teaching methods. One prominent figure in this field is Marc Prensky. Prensky (2004) is an advocate for the use of technology in the classroom, claiming that since today's students are digital natives, technology can effectively meet their diverse learning demands and learning styles. Prensky's research highlights how crucial it is to modify teaching strategies to use digital tools and resources to improve student learning and results. It is also beneficial for tracking the progress of students. By employing digital tools teachers can track and analyze student progress over time and identify areas for further improvement.

Promoting self-directed learning is also very essential in teaching ESP courses and it can be the sixth step to teaching students effectively. This element will encourage students to take charge of their learning journey, exploring additional resources and engaging in self-study. Malcolm Knowles has extensively discussed promoting self-

directed learning. According to Knowles' idea, adult learners would rather be in charge of all aspects of their education, including designing, carrying out, and reviewing their courses. His research paved the way for our current understanding of how adults and children learn differently and the significance of creating learning settings that support independence and self-direction.

The final step can be reflecting and revising. Applied linguists, Rubin and Thompson are known for their research on language learning strategies. Rubin's and Thompson's (1994) work emphasizes the importance of reflection in understanding one's learning process and making informed decisions about when and how to use different language learning strategies. In a nutshell, these probable elements hopefully help to resolve the challenges encountered during implementation to address them. Further to find out the effectiveness of these approaches feedback from participants and deep analysis are about to take. In this regard, it is suggested to recapitulate the key findings and their implications for ESP teaching practices.

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